

Supplemental Table 8. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between income and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Income categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG decreased if low-income; odds of insufficient GWG increased if low-income		0-200% of poverty line >200% of poverty line	No	S
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents <18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337		NS association between poverty level and GWG	0-100% of federal poverty line >100% of federal poverty line	Yes	NS
Bombard, J.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Multi-state study involving women who responded to the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2005-06	14 990	Significantly higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in low-income women (as compared to high-income women); with adjusted OR, near-low-income women (as compared to high income women) had significantly higher odds of having insufficient GWG than adequate GWG	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG between low-income and higher income; with adjusted OR, NS difference in odds of excessive GWG vs adequate GWG for low-income or near-low-income women (as compared to high income women), and NS difference in odds of insufficient vs adequate GWG in low-income women as compared to high-income women	0-100% of federal poverty line 101-250% of federal poverty line >250% of federal poverty line	No	S & NS
Chaffee, B. W.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Individuals in the 1979 cohort of the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth (age 14-21 in 1979) who gave birth before the age of 40	4 780		Risk ratio for excessive GWG based on growing up in a household that was <200% or <100% of federal poverty line was NS for all women (subdivided by race/ethnicity: non-Black, non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic, and non-Black Hispanic)	<100% of federal poverty line (value for household in which the woman grew up) <200% of federal poverty line (value for household in which the woman grew up)	No	NS†
Chagarlamudi, H.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women attending an outpatient obstetrics/gynecology clinic that mainly serves a low-income community (2012-13) in North Carolina	410		NS effect on odds of having excessive or insufficient GWG (as compared to adequate GWG) by low-income status (indicated by Medicaid or lack of insurance)	Medicaid or lack of insurance Other	Yes	NS†

Chang, T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women aged 15-24 years living in large US cities from 1998-2000; national weights were used to make data representative of births in all large US cities (populations of >200,000); all women were part of the "Fragile Families and Child Wellbeing Study"	1,034 (unweighted)		NS association between poverty level and excessive or insufficient GWG	0-49% of federal poverty line 50-99% of federal poverty line 100-199% of federal poverty line 200-299% of federal poverty line ≥300% of federal poverty line	No	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to household income	<\$15,000 \$15,000-30,000 >\$30,000	Yes	NS
Chasan-Taber, L.		USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Hispanic (primarily Puerto Rican), low-income women receiving prenatal care at a public clinic from 2000-03	770		Household income was not significantly associated with GWG	<\$15,000 \$15,000-30,000 >\$30,000	Yes	NS
	2008										
Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293		Income not associated with adequacy of GWG	<\$15,000 \$15,000-30,000 >\$30,000	Yes	NS
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632		NS difference in risk of excessive or insufficient GWG according to Medicaid status	Medicaid use (yes/no)	No	NS†
Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy based on enrollment in Medicaid/TANF/Food Stamps		Enrollment in Medicaid/TANF/Food Stamps (yes/no)	Yes	S†

D'Angelo, D. V.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	PRAMS data from women who gave birth in 27 different states in 2008, all of which had a PRAMS survey response rate of 65% or greater	35 980		NS difference in adjusted odds of gaining >35 lbs vs ≤35 lbs in women with Medicaid as compared to private medical insurance	Medicaid Private insurance	No	NS†
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	Overweight women: higher odds of insufficient GWG if enrolled in Medicaid	NS effect of WIC enrollement on GWG adequacy across all groups; NS effect of Medicaid enrollement in all groups but overweight (higher risk of insufficient GWG)	Medicaid use (yes/no) WIC enrollment (yes/no)	No	S† & NS†
Gaillard, R.	2013	Netherlands	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 959		NS effect of monthly household income on odds of excessive GWG	<€1,600 €1,6000-2,2000 >€2,220	No	NS
Groth, S. W.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	White and Black women aged 18-35 with a BMI between 18.5 and 34.9 kg/m2 who participated in a RCT from 2009-14	774	Among Black women: low-income women (<185% of poverty line) with obesity gained significantly more weight than higher income women (>185% of poverty line) with obesity in one of two gene groups (FTO gene), but this difference was not observed among other BMI groups or when all BMI groups were combined; among White women: higher income normal-weight women had significantly lower weight gain in both gene groups (FTO and GNB3), but this difference was not observed in other BMI groups or when all BMI groups were combined	In most BMI groups and gene groups, income was not significantly associated with GWG	<185% of poverty line >185% of poverty line	No	S & NS
Guilloty, N.	2015	USA (Puerto Rico)	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in northern Puerto Rico from 2011-14	160		NS association between GWG adequacy and income	<\$20,000 ≥\$20,000	Yes	NS
Haile, Z. T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the population-based Infant Feeding Practices Study II from 2005-07	2 053	Significant differences in GWG adequacy by poverty-to-income ratio		Poverty-to-income ratios: <185% 185-349% ≥350%	No	S
Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300	Significant differences in GWG adequacy according to equivalized income (divided in quartiles); higher average cumulative neighbourhood deprivation was associated with increased risk of insufficient GWG (did not vary by ethnicity) and excessive GWG (only for White women); persistent low deprivation was associated with decreased risk of insufficient and excessive GWG (vs. high deprivation); upward mobility was associated with decreased risk of insufficient GWG across all ethnicities		Equivalized income measured in quartiles	No	S

Hickey, C. A.	1977a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806		NS association between insufficient GWG and household income, per capita income, source of income, utility disconnections (noted as being an indirect measure of financial stress), and participation in income-related assistance programs	Annual household income: <\$5,000 \$5,000-9,999 \$10,000-14,999 \$15,000-19,999 ≥\$20,000	Yes	NS
Huynh, M.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Primiparous women who gave birth from 1999-2001 in New York City, were ≥20 years old, and either White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, or Hispanic	56 911	Excessive GWG more likely in women living in low SES neighborhood compared to medium or high SES neighborhood; significant difference in prevalence of excessive GWG in women who use Medicaid when analyzed according to level of education (no sub-group analysis)		Medicaid vs other insurance	No	S†
Jung, Y.M.	2017	Korea	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth to term infants and resided in a single city in South Korea	75		NS difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) by mean maternal age; NS difference in total GWG by household income (<3,000,000 won vs ≥3,000,000 won)	<3,000,000 won (Korean currency) ≥3,000,000 won	No	NS
Koh, H.	2013	Singapore	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG guideline by Wong et al., 2000	All women who delivered at a specific hospital from Jan-Apr 2008 (approximately 30% of infants in Singapore are delivered at this hospital every year)	1 166	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate): subsidized paying class for hospital (vs private paying class)	NS effect of paying class (subsidized vs private) on odds of excessive GWG	Hospital paying class: Subsidized Private	No	S† & NS†
Koleilat, M.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Primarily Hispanic women, all with a low-income and enrolled in the Public Health Foundation Enterprises WIC Program in Southern California	23 840	Higher odds of excessive GWG if above federal poverty line (>100% vs <100% of federal poverty level)		<100% federal poverty line >100% federal poverty line	Yes	S
Kominiarek, M. A.	2018b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Large multi-site study with random selection of women who gave birth at one of the sites from 2008-11	29 861	Significant differences in GWG adequacy (inadequate, adequate, excessive) according to insurance type (private, government-assisted, uninsured)		Insurance type: Private Government-assisted Uninsured	No	S†

Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if of lower-middle or middle income group (compared to upper-middle income group); lower odds of insufficient GWG if lower-middle income (compared to upper-middle income); lower odds of excessive GWG if from highest income group (vs upper-middle income)	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG if of lowest income group (as compared to upper-middle income); NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG for lowest, middle and highest income groups (as compared to upper-middle income)	No thresholds provided for income in each category	No	S & NS
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619	Lower odds of excessive GWG if on Medicaid at any point in pregnancy		Medicaid use (yes/no)	No	S†
Laraia, B.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women aged ≥16 years participating in the multi-site Pregnancy, Infection, and Nutrition cohort in North Carolina from January 2001 - June 2005	1 041	Marginally food insecure combined with high dietary restraint have higher GWG (same effect when limited to low-income marginally food insecure); marginally food insecure combined with low dietary restraint have lower GWG (same effect when limited to low-income marginally food insecure)		Limited to households ≤400% of the federal income/poverty ratio; measured as a continuous variable	No	S†
Lindberg, S.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at UW Health from 2007-12	7 385	Factors increasing odds of excessive GWG: neighborhood with low economic hardship (compared to moderate); decreased odds of excessive GWG: having Medicaid (vs commercial insurance), living in a neighborhood with low economic hardship (vs moderate); factors increasing odds of insufficient GWG: Medicaid (compared to commercial insurance), neighborhood with high economic hardship (compared to moderate)	NS effect of living in neighborhood with low economic hardship (vs moderate) on odds of insufficient GWG	Medicaid vs commercial insurance	No	S†
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM 1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥15 years old	5 554	Higher prevalence of insufficient GWG if low household income (as compared to high income)	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG according to income	No income thresholds provided for household income categories	No	S & NS
Nunnery, D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women attending a WIC clinic (for low-income women) in 2014 who were receiving WIC as a maternity client and were ≥18 years old	160		In multivariate regression: NS association between monthly income and odds of excessive GWG	\$0-500 \$501-1,000 ≥\$1,000	Yes	NS

Park, J. H.	2011	Korea	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified (no official guidelines in Korea)	Single-site study of women who gave birth at a university hospital from 2005-07	2 311		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to low economic status	<100 x 10 ⁴ won/month 100-299 x 10 ⁴ won/month >300 x 10 ⁴ won/month; (Korean currency: 1USD = 1500 won)	No	NS
Platner, M. H.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in New York City from 2008-2012	515 148	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG based on insurance type (considered as a proxy for low-income; Medicaid, other, private, self-pay)		Insurance type: Medicaid Private Self-pay Other	No	S†
Provenzano, A. M.	2015	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Women who received prenatal care at a multispecialty group practice in Massachusetts (single-site)	2 128		NS association between adequacy of GWG and material hardship during pregnancy or from age 18 to pregnancy	Material hardship defined as having ever received public assistance, welfare or lacked basic necessities	No	NS†
Rosal, M. C.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study involving Non-Latina White and Latina women	571		NS effect of insurance (commercial/private vs public) on odds of excessive or insufficient GWG	Insurance type: Commercial/private Public	No	NS†
Scholl, T. O.	1995	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Women age 12-29 with a low-income and a normal BMI; most women were Puerto Rican Hispanic or Black (data from Camden Study)	274		NS association between adequacy of GWG rate and Medicaid use	Medicaid use (yes/no)	Yes	NS†
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥18 years old	250 857	Decreased odds of excessive GWG if on Medicaid	NS effect of Medicaid use on odds of insufficient GWG	Medicaid use (yes/no)	No	S† & NS†
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988	Lower odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if enrolled in WIC services; significant differences in general GWG adequacy according to income (divided into quartiles of annual family income)	NS effect of prenatal care payer (Medicaid vs not Medicaid) on general adequacy of GWG (looked at distribution of women in insufficient, adequate and excessive categories); NS association between odds of insufficient GWG and income	WIC enrollment (yes/no) Income quartiles: \$0-10,400 \$10,400-17,186 \$17,186-30,000 >\$30,000	Yes	S & NS
Wells, C. S.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-02 Colorado Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	4 528		NS effect of WIC enrollment or having prenatal care paid by Medicaid, on adequacy of GWG	WIC enrollment (yes/no) Prenatal care paid by Medicaid	No	NS†
Woolfolk, C. L.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of adolescents who gave birth in the USA in 2012	211 403	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (prevalence of insufficient, adequate, excessive) according to WIC status		WIC enrollment (yes/no)	Yes	S†

† Study used a proxy measure for income (e.g., use of a social assistance program)